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12.00.02 - КОНСТИТУЦИОННИЙ ҲУҚУҚ, МАЪМУРИЙ ҲУҚУҚ, МОЛИЯ ВА БОЖХОНА ҲУҚУҚИ / КОНСТИТУЦИОННОЕ ПРАВО; АДМИНИСТРАТИВНОЕ ПРАВО; ФИНАНСОВОЕ ПРАВО / CONSTITUTIONAL LAW; ADMINISTRATIVE LAW; FINANCIAL RIGHT

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12.00.03 - ФУҚАРОЛИК ҲУҚУҚИ. ТАДБИРКОРЛИК ҲУҚУҚИ. ОИЛА ҲУҚУҚИ. ХАЛҚАРО ХУСУСИЙ ҲУҚУҚ / ГРАЖДАНСКОЕ ПРАВО; ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСКОЕ ПРАВО; СЕМЕЙНОЕ ПРАВО; МЕЖДУНАРОДНОЕ ЧАСТНОЕ ПРАВО / CIVIL LAW; BUSINESS LAW; FAMILY LAW; PRIVATE INTERNATIONAL LAW

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1. Боймуродов Ботир Панжи ўғли ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИДА ҚОНУНЧИЛИК ТАШАББУСИ ХУҚУҚИГА ОИД ҚОНУНЧИЛИК ТАҲЛИЛИ.....	5
2. Мухамедов Ҳайдарали Мелиевич ДАВЛАТ ВА ХУҚУҚ ТАРИХИ ФАНИНИНГ ХУҚУҚШУНОС КАДРЛАР ТАЙЁРЛАШДА ТУТГАН ЎРНИ ВА АҲАМИЯТИ.....	14
3. Narimanov Bekzod Abduvaliyevich NODAVLAT NOTIJORAT TASHKILOTLARINING BMT BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH MAQSADLARIGA ERISHISH JARAYONIDAGI ISHTIROKINI FAOLLASHTIRISH.....	23
4. Ismoilova Nazokatxon Shuxratjon qizi MA'LUMOTLAR TAQSIMLANGAN REYESTRI TEXNOLOGIYASI VA SMART- KONTRAKTLARNI FUQAROLIK HUQUQIY TARTIBGA SOLISH KONSEPSIYASIGA DOIR MILLIY QONUNCHILIKNING TANQIDIY TAHLILI.....	30
5. Махмудова Лола Асат кизи ПРАВОВОЙ ЗАПРЕТ РИБЫ В ИСЛАМСКОМ ПРАВЕ: СРАВНИТЕЛЬНО-ПРАВОВОЙ АНАЛИЗ И ВОПРОСЫ ГАРМОНИЗАЦИИ С ЧАСТНЫМ ПРАВОМ.....	38
6. Муродов Мухлис Матназар ўғли КРЕДИТ ШАРТНОМАЛАРИ БИЛАН БОҒЛИҚ ФУҚАРОЛИК ИШЛАРИДА ИШТИРОК ЭТУВЧИ ШАХСЛАР ВА УЛАРНИНГ ХУҚУҚИЙ МАҚОМИ.....	50
7. Khamidov Nurmukhammad Orif ugli FEATURES OF SOME CRIMES COMMITTED BY OFFICIALS.....	59
8. Mamajanov Abrorbek Mirabdullayevich ZAHARLI MODDALARNI QONUNGA XILOF RAVISHDA MUOMALAGA KIRITGANLIK UCHUN JINOIY JAVOBGARLIK BILAN BOG'LIQ AYRIM MULOHAZALAR.....	65
9. Shamsidinov Zayniddin Ziyovidinovich PROBLEMS OF THE CURRENT COMPLIANCE CONTROL SYSTEM IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.....	73
10. Sunnatov Vohid Toshmurodovich TOVLAMACHILIK JINOYATINING AYRIM JIHATLRI.....	80
11. Nodirov Muzaffar Axmadovich, Tursunmurodov Komron Turg'un o'g'li SO'ROQ QILISH TERGOV HARAKATIDA VIDEOYOZUV TEXNOLOGIYALARINI QO'LLASH IMKONIYATLARI.....	87
12. Нурманов Холбек Раҳматилла угли БОРЬБА С КИБЕРПРЕСТУПНОСТЬЮ - ОПЫТ СИНГАПУРА.....	101

12.00.08-УГОЛОВНОЕ ПРАВО. УГОЛОВНО-ИСПОЛНИТЕЛЬНОЕ ПРАВО

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FEATURES OF SOME CRIMES COMMITTED BY OFFICIALS

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ANNOTATION

In this scientific article, the object of the crime of career fraud and its signs, their specific criminal-legal aspects, in particular, their provision in the criminal law, as well as the lack of a clear interpretation of the concept of "serious damage" in the norms of these crimes, raise many questions. Recommendations are given on clarifying the exact scope of the crime of forgery and prevention. Scientific proposals have also been developed in this regard.

Keywords: forgery, objective side of the crime, forgery crimes, in significant damage, prevention issues, government authority.

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**МАНСАБДОР ШАХСЛАР ТОМОНИДАН СОДИР ЭТИЛАДИГАН АЙРИМ
ЖИНОЯТЛАРНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОСЛИГИ**

АННОТАЦИЯ

Мазкур илмий мақолада мансаб сохтакорлиги жиноятининг объекти ва унинг белгилари, уларнинг ўзига хос жиноят-ҳуқуқий жиҳатлари, хусусан, уларнинг жиноят қонунчилигида назарда тутилиши, шунингдек, мазкур жиноятлар белгиланган нормалардаги “жиддий зиён” тушунчасининг аниқ талқини йўқлиги кўплаб саволларни келтириб чиқараётганлиги шундан келиб чиқиб, мансаб сохтакорлиги жиноятининг аниқ доираси ва профилактикаси масалаларини аниқлаштириш бўйича тавсиялар берилган. Шунингдек бу борадаги илмий таклифлар ҳам ишлаб чиқилган.

Калит сўзлар: мансаб сохтакорлиги, жиноят объекти, мансабдорлик жиноятлари, “жиддий зиён”, профилактика масалалари, давлат ҳокимияти, бошқарув органлари.

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ОСОБЕННОСТИ НЕКОТОРЫХ ПРЕСТУПЛЕНИЙ, СОВЕРШАЕМЫХ ДОЛЖНОСТНЫМИ ЛИЦАМИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной научной статье предмет преступления служебного мошенничества и его признаки, их конкретные уголовно-правовые аспекты, в частности, их положение в уголовном законе, а также отсутствие четкого толкования понятия «крупный ущерб» в нормах указанных преступлений вызывают много вопросов. Даны рекомендации по уточнению точного состава преступления служебного подлога и его предупреждению. Также разработаны научные предложения по данному поводу.

Ключевые слова: должностной подлог, объект преступления, должностные преступления, существенный вред, вопросы профилактики, государственная власть, органы управления.

In Uzbekistan, in order to build a democratic state governed by the rule of law and form a civil society, consistent and phased judicial and legal reforms are being carried out through promising programs, the main attention is paid to ensuring the rule of law and strengthening the guarantees of individual rights and freedoms. As the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov noted, "One of the most important directions at the present stage is the consistent democratization and liberalization of the judicial and legal system, aimed at strengthening the rule of law and legality, reliable protection of the rights and interests of the individual"[1].

In particular, it is no exaggeration to say that the approval of the Action Strategy on five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 and its second direction, entitled "Priority directions for ensuring the rule of law and further reforming the judicial and legal system[2]," today serve as the main program for preventing crime, corruption and official crimes in society and reducing the level of their commission, as well as coordinating activities to combat crime and prevent offenses in this area, improving organizational and legal mechanisms for combating corruption, and increasing the effectiveness of anti-corruption measures.

At the same time, the issues of clearly defining the scope of official crimes, their characteristics, and further improving the qualification and prevention of these types of crimes are currently relevant. Because the concept and scope of official crimes are currently causing many debates among both theoretical scholars and specialists working in the field of law enforcement. Representatives of this field emphasize that official crimes are acts that cause significant damage or serious harm to state, public interests or the rights and legally protected interests of citizens as a result of an official using the authority and official powers granted to him or deliberately violating his duties[3].

From this point of view, many questions arise regarding which specific articles of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan recognize crimes as official crimes, the extent to which measures to prevent these crimes are organized, as well as the lack of a clear interpretation of the concept of "serious damage" in the norms defining these crimes. Based on this, there is a need to clarify the concept of the crime of official forgery, the specific scope of these crimes, and issues of their prevention.

Despite the intensive efforts to combat crime, in particular official crimes, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the influence of external factors on crime, the development of free market relations is

leading to the emergence of new types of crime, and the crime of official fraud is increasing. In this regard, it is urgent to further improve this institution, eliminate existing problems, and systematically develop, implement and implement preventive measures.

Because, as the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev emphasized, “The era of going beyond the scope of authority and interfering in all spheres, ignoring the interests of the Motherland and the people, and using the name of the “office” for the sake of one’s own interests has passed. That is, no citizen should be held accountable on the basis of fake evidence, slander, and libel[4].”

Finding a solution to the above issues requires, first of all, an analysis of legislative acts, making appropriate amendments and additions to them, thereby clarifying the scope of official crimes, qualifying these crimes, determining a system of specific measures for their prevention, and further expanding and strengthening them.

According to Article 2 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, “The state expresses the will of the people and serves its interests. State bodies and officials are responsible to society and citizens.” These requirements of the Basic Law increase the responsibility of officials in the mechanisms of activity of state power, public service and local self-government bodies or in their spheres, determine the obligations of the state apparatus to citizens. The social danger of official fraud, abuse, bribery or organized crime in the system of the state apparatus leads to the disruption or damage of this very system. It undermines the political, economic and legal system of the state. The crime of official fraud cannot be imagined without official crimes. Abuse of office is considered a general component of official fraud.

Official crimes are crimes against the order of the activities of government and administrative bodies - these are actions that affect the normal, legally regulated activities of state and local government and administrative bodies, as well as enterprises, institutions and organizations, regardless of the form of ownership, committed by officials of certain government and administrative bodies using their powers, as well as by persons performing management functions on a special assignment (authorization) [5].

In this regard, it is possible to study not only the basic laws of individual types of official crimes, but also their place in general crime, their characteristics in relation to the management system, their development paths and directions, which can only be carried out through scientific research. It makes it possible to identify effective methods of warning and preventing crimes of official fraud, and to determine measures of social influence.

As we know, the only means of determining the criminality of a socially dangerous act, that is, its criminalization, is the composition of the crime. The composition of the crime consists of a set of objective and subjective signs of the crime. By objective signs, we mean the object and objective side of the composition of the crime.

The object of the crime is the social relations protected by the Criminal Code, to which criminal aggression is directed and to which harm can be caused through this aggression[6].

Indeed, in the theory of criminal law, it is established that official crimes have a single general object, that is, the normal activity of the state apparatus, which corresponds to the structure of the state. The above-mentioned legal features of the crime of official fraud create the opportunity to identify its specific and direct objects. Most legal scholars believe that the specific object of official crimes is social relations arising from the normal activities of the state or public apparatus, covering various spheres of social life, namely, the national economy, culture, personnel training, ensuring public order, and others.[7]

Determining the object of the crime of official fraud is of theoretical and practical importance. Correctly determining the object: a) allows you to distinguish similar criminal laws for this type of crime; b) ensures the correct qualification of the crime committed by an official; c) determines the amount of punishment depending on the degree of socially dangerous behavior; d) creates an opportunity to determine measures to prevent the occurrence of situations that lead to the occurrence of this crime. The problems of the object of crime are given great importance in the theory of criminal law.

As is known, social relations in society are measured by various social values, the value of life, spiritual wealth and material condition, labor or other achievements. It can be directed to the same social relations or to social relations with two or more objects. In such cases, the qualitative or quantitative indicators of individual social relations are different in crimes.

The social danger of harm caused to social relations is not the same. By determining the features of the composition of such a crime, such cases create difficulties in determining the direction of a special part of the Criminal Code, creating complex situations in the qualification of crimes[8]. It should be especially noted that, in accordance with the rules established in society, jurisprudence determines the belonging of the committed crime to one or another section of the Criminal Code, based on the value of social relations.

The harm caused to social relations, which is embodied in the state apparatus, is manifested in the sphere of activity of an official in the field of official fraud. In most of the investigated criminal cases, these signs are emphasized as a necessary sign of the composition of the crime of official fraud.

In this process, the protection of the interests of government bodies and public associations from criminal encroachments is assessed as one of the priority tasks of the fight against crime. Because the protection of the interests of government bodies and public associations from criminal encroachments is a prerequisite for the effective implementation of the policy of democratization of state power and administration. In this regard, the protection of social relations that ensure the normal functioning of government bodies, administration and public associations from criminal encroachments is one of the important areas of activity of law enforcement agencies[9].

The direct object of the crime is social relations that arise within the framework of the normal functioning of state power and administration bodies.

An additional direct object is social relations aimed at ensuring the legitimate rights and interests of citizens. The subject of official forgery is official documents[10].

The definition of the specific object of the crime of official forgery emphasizes that the normal functioning of state or public administration forms the basis of this crime. Accordingly, it is necessary to define the concept of apparatus. Firstly, it is necessary to determine the level and boundaries of the state's management activities in the political, economic and cultural spheres; secondly, to determine the list of bodies representing state management; to determine the scope of activities of officials who determine the normal functioning of the state apparatus. In the theory of state and law, the concept of state management has been studied almost extensively, in which all bodies that make up the state mechanism are considered. These include the Oliy Majlis and local councils of people's deputies, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan and executive bodies of power, local supervisory bodies, local self-government committees, etc.

The object of this crime may also be the normal activities of public organizations that represent a certain direction of state management. These include collective farms established by government bodies, self-governing mahalla councils, trade union committees at the republican and regional levels, and at the city level. The normal functioning of such organizations, primarily the implementation of the state executive and management basis, determines the commonality of property. The system of such organizations should also include organizations operating at the expense of state funds, operating on the basis of state orders.

The types of public organizations also include party or youth organizations, educational and cultural associations, scientific production organizations, and others.

In judicial practice, officials of public organizations are also qualified as official crimes. The above-listed organizations are considered the connecting basis of the people with the basis of state administration. In order to correctly resolve the issues facing public organizations, their leaders and other employees are assigned official functions. From this it can be concluded that a special management apparatus is operated in the system of public organizations, which can be conditionally called public administration.

Thus, the interests of society, the interests of citizens are determined by the correct functioning system of the state and public administration. The commonality of the tasks and functions of these social relations can serve as a basis for considering them as objects of joint criminal law protection.

At the same time, the system of public administration should not include private enterprises, family production organizations, religious organizations, and private commercial organizations. Such organizations cannot form a state or public mechanism. The issues of responsibility for the actions of the leaders of such organizations should be excluded from the system of official crimes.

The object of the crime of official fraud is much broader than the object of other crimes against the order of government, it implies social relations that are wider than the scope of social relations associated with the delimitation of the sphere of government. In official crimes, social relations related to government are only an integral part of the special object of these crimes, as part of the normal functioning of the state apparatus.

A brief analysis of the special object of the crime of official fraud allows us to draw the following conclusions. In particular, the correct functioning of the state system, manifested in the basis of state or public administration, is a set of relations that arise on the basis of a process that meets the requirements of the time. Strict adherence to state discipline, unconditional execution of state and government decisions, strict adherence to social legislation and strict adherence to the protection of the rights and interests of citizens protected by law are considered correct activities[11].

We will cover the special object of the crime of official fraud mainly based on the conclusions of the analysis of criminal cases. To address this issue, a special questionnaire was included to name the types of social relations (the sphere of the state or public apparatus) that were seriously damaged.

In the criminal law literature, various approaches have been taken to distinguish between the specific and direct objects of the crime of official fraud. Some authors believe that these objects largely coincide. Others believe that it is possible to consider the direct object in official crimes. M.D. Lysov, sharply criticizing this idea, says that this approach to the issue theoretically creates insurmountable difficulties in qualifying crimes. In this regard, in our opinion, the criticized idea leads to the unity of the direct object with the criminal consequence, as a result of which the object of the crime loses its independent significance.

Most authors distinguish between the specific object and the direct object. However, there is no consensus among them. B.S. Nikiforov says that the direct object of official crimes is "specific conditions of the proper functioning of the state apparatus". And B.S. Utevskiy says different branches of the national economy and management. M.D. Lysov says that the basis of the signs of duties and the direct object of the official crime is based on some functions of management.

In conclusion, as a result of the interpreted opinions, it can be concluded that all of them are engaged not in determining the direct object of an official crime, but in determining the direct objects of specific criminal acts. In this case, the concept of direct object is replaced by the concept of substantially caused damage. Moreover, such a definition of the direct object does not correspond to the essence of certain types of official crimes. The special object of a crime unites a group of homogeneous direct objects of crimes. The direct object of the corpus delicti is the social relations to which these crimes are directly and indirectly encroached. The direct object clarifies the special object of the crime. From the foregoing, it can be concluded that the object of official forgery is the normal functioning of state authorities and administration.

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